

THE EFFECT OF FIBRE CHEMICAL TREATMENTS ON HEMP REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Glass or carbon fibres are traditionally used as reinforcement in engineering composites. The increasing ecological and environmental concerns have led to the use of natural fibres as renewable alternatives [1]. Among them, hemp fibre offers the best mechanical properties as well as abundant availability. However, the hemp fibre, same as other natural fibres, has the issues of fiber/matrix bonding and moisture absorption [2]. Hydrophilic nature of hemp fibre causes a weak bonding with hydrophobic polymers matrix and the property deterioration during service [3].

Chemical treatments are needed to modify the surface of fibre, aiming at improving the adhesion with polymer matrix and reducing the hydrophilicity of the fibre. Alkalization, acetylation and the combination were used in this study to treat the hemp fibre. The effects of the chemical treatments on the fibre and the hemp fibre reinforced composites were investigated.

2 Materials and Experimental

Hemp fibres were obtained from Eco Fibre Industries. The fibres were first washed and dried. For alkalization treatment, the fibres were soaked in 6% NaOH at room temperature for 3 hours. For acetylation treatments, the fibres were soaked in acetic acid first then immersed into acetic anhydride at room temperature for 3 hours. For the combined treatment, the fibres were treated with 6% NaOH, followed by acetylation treatment. After the chemical treatment, the fibres were washed with distilled water and dried in an 80°C for 24 hours.

Unsaturated polyester was used to make the hemp reinforced composites. Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide was used as curing catalyst. The composites were

prepared using vacuum assisted resin infusion. Hemp fiber volume fraction was kept at about 40%.

The chemical analysis was used to determine the percentage of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin in the fibre before and after treatments. FTIR, DSC and SEM were used to characterize the fibres.

The flexural test was performed by using a computer controlled universal testing machine of 10kN load cell. The ASTM D-790 test method was followed and a span to depth ratio of 16:1 was maintained. The cross-head speed of 2mm/min was applied. The shear properties of the samples were measured accordance to ASTM D-5379 standard. At least five specimens of each sample were used and reported the average values.

Mechanical properties of the composites were tested using three point bending and shear tests.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Chemical Constituents of Fibres

Natural fibres are complex in structure. They are generally lignocellulosic, consisting of helically wound cellulose microfibrils in an amorphous matrix of lignin and hemicelluloses [4]. Mechanical properties of fibre are dominated by the cellulose content and microfibril angle. A high cellulose content and low microfibril angle are desirable properties in a fibre to be used as reinforcement in composites [5-7].

Table 1. Chemical constituents of untreated and NaOH treated hemp fibres.

Fibres	Cellulose (%)	Hemi-cellulose	Lignin (%)
untreated	80.5	6.2	7.3
6% NaOH	84.1	4.9	5.0
10% NaOH	94.2	5.0	3.5

NaOH and other chemical treatments can remove the impurity of hemp fibre, clean its surface and degrade lignin. It effectively increases the fibre's cellulose content and provides much cleaner and smoother surface for polymer matrix adhesion [1, 5, 7-8]. Table 1 shows the chemical constituents of hemp fibres before and after NaON treatment.

3.2 FTIR Analysis

The FTIR spectra of untreated, alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylation treated fibres are given in Fig. 1 and Table 2. The broad band at 3407 cm^{-1} is the characteristic band for -O-H stretching for untreated fibres [9-10]. Chemical treatments such as alkali and acetylation shifted the band to 3434 cm^{-1} and 3419 cm^{-1} respectively, and increased its intensity. This is the indication of the reduction of hydrogen bonding in cellulosic hydroxyl groups, thereby increasing -OH concentration. As a result the hydrophilic nature of the fibre is decreased and more reactive -OH group is exposed to react with the matrix.

Table 2. Infrared transmittance peaks (cm^{-1}) of untreated and treated fibres

Fibre	O-H stretching (cellulose)	C=O stretching (hemi-c)	C=O stretching (hemi-c)	C=O stretching (lignin)
Untreated	3407	1737	1643	1249
Alkali	3434	-	1650	1256
Acetylati	3419	1726	1643	1253

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of the fibres.

The band 1737 cm^{-1} is correspondent to the C=O stretching in the actyl groups of hemicelluloses of the untreated fibres [11]. This band disappears for the alkali treated samples. This indicates that hemicelluloses were removed from the fibre surface. For the acetylated fibre, this band is shifted to 1726 cm^{-1} .

The band at 1249 cm^{-1} for untreated fibre is corresponded to the C=O stretching in the aromatic ring of lignin [11]. For alkali and acetylation treated fibres this band was up-shifted to 1256 cm^{-1} and 1253 cm^{-1} respectively. From these results, it proves that lignin attached on the surface of fibre was removed by the designated chemical treatments.

In summary, the FTIR analysis confirms the chemical constituents results, which is that alkali and acetylation treatments remove the hemicellulose and lignin from the fibre. As a result, it effectively increases the cellulose content in the fibre, more importantly, it exposes more reactive -OH group in cellulose to react with the matrix, therefore increase the bonding between fibre and matrix.

3.3 DSC Analysis of Fibres

DSC analysis enables to identify the chemical activity occurring in the fibre as heat was applied [12-13]. Fig. 2 shows the thermal response of the untreated and chemical treated hemp fibres as a function of temperature. Both untreated and treated fibres exhibited one broad endothermic peak between the temperature of 70-90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and one exothermic peak between 260-380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The first endothermic peak corresponds to the evaporation of moisture absorbed by the fibre. In this region some variations of thermal energy were observed with the effect of alkali and acetylation treatment compared to the untreated fibre. This was due to the changes of fibre moisture absorption after treatment [1]. Heat flow rate for moisture evaporation on untreated fibre is observed less than the treated fibres. This is because less moisture was absorbed by the treated fibres, therefore it requires higher energy to evaporate.

The exothermic peaks in Fig. 2 correspond to the decomposition of cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin of the fibres. In natural fibres, lignin degrades at the temperature around 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ while the other constituents such as hemicelluloses and cellulose degrades at higher temperatures [14]. For untreated

fibre, the exothermic peaks were observed at temperatures of 260-370°C, while all treated fibres showed exothermic peak at higher temperatures, between 300-385°C. This was presumably due to the partial removal of lignin and hemicelluloses from the fibres by alkali and acetylation treatment. As a result, thermal stability of the treated fibres was increased as compared with the untreated fibre. In addition to this, hydrophobicity of the treated fibre was increased as the tendency of water molecules held by the lignin and hemicelluloses were reduced.

3.4 SEM Analysis of Fibres

Fig. 3 shows SEM micrographs of the surface of hemp fibres before and after treatments. The SEM image of the untreated hemp fibres shows some impurity substance on the surface. Chemical treatment certainly removed most of the impurity. The surface is clean. The alkali treated fibre demonstrates more rough surface as compared with the untreated fibre. Several chemical groups (in a pattern of partition) are formed on the surface of the fibre, which hold the fibrils together to form tightly packed fibre bundle. This pattern can also enhance the friction between the fibre and matrix, which makes the fibre pull out more difficult. The formation of the rough surface in the alkali treated fibre is due to the removal of hemicelluloses and lignin constituents by alkali treatment, which results in more reactive hydroxyl group exposed on the fibre surface [12-13]. The surface roughness facilitates better interfacial adhesion with the matrix and thus to get higher mechanical properties of their resultant composites.

Fig. 2. DSC analysis of untreated, alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylation treated hemp fibres.

On the other hand, the acetylated fibre shows a bit rougher and brittle surface as compared with other fibres. Several transverse cracks appear on the fibre surface. This may be due to the reaction between acetyl groups with the fibre's hydroxyl groups and thus the molecular orientation of the cellulose backbone changed. As a result, the fibre becomes rougher and stiffer in character [9]. This reduces the hydrophilicity of the fibre and provides better bonding with the matrix materials.

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of the untreated and treated hemp fibres.

3.5 Mechanical Properties of Composites

The effect of chemical treatments in relation to the interface bonding characteristics between the fibre and matrix can be reflected on their flexural strength properties. Fig. 4 shows the stress-strain curves of untreated and treated composite samples. From Fig. 4 and 6 it is observed that flexural strength of alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylated fibre composite samples showed 12%, 33% and 17% improvements in strength properties compared to the untreated fibre sample. The improvement in strength can attribute: (1) the increase of cellulose content after treatment; (2) the increase of chemical bonding between fibre and matrix, because the removal of lignin and hemicelluloses expose the more $-OH$ groups to react with matrix [7, 10]. (3) the increase of mechanical bonding because of fibre surface roughness [15].

Fig. 4. Flexural properties of untreated, alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylation treated composites.

Fig. 5. Shear properties of untreated, alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylation treated composites.

The stress-strain curves in Fig. 4 show that acetylation treated samples have the highest flexural strength compared to the other treated samples. This may be because the acetylation treatment has the additional etching function to the fibre surface. Non-uniform etching increase surface roughness and fibre contact area with matrix.

It is observed that alkali+acetylation treatment has a slightly higher flexural strength than the single alkali treatment but lower than the single acetylation treatment. The results from this study has confirmed that both alkali and acetylation treatments has the effect of removing lignin and hemicelluloses. Two contiguous treatments can cause excessive removal of lignin and hemicelluloses, which act as a cementing material to hold the cellulose in fibre structure. As a result, the fibre becomes weaker in strength.

In the shear test, one side of the V-notched specimen was fixed in the fixture and other side displaced vertically along the fibre direction. The stress transfer of the composites initiated through the matrix slides over the fibre surface [16]. As a result frictional stress transfer occurs along the fibre-matrix interface. From Fig. 5 and 6 it is observed that alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylated fibre composite samples showed 36.43%, 19.11% and 43.73% higher strength properties compared to the untreated fibre sample. This was presumably due to the higher surface roughness (Fig. 3) of the treated fibre contributed good bonding with the matrix and provided greater frictional stress transfer along the interface.

Fig 6. Flexural and shear properties of the composites.

4. Conclusion

Different chemical treatments, including alkali, acetylation and alkali+acetylation, are applied on hemp fibre. The chemical treatments partially remove lignin and hemicelluloses from the fibre, therefore increase the cellulose content of the fibre. Removal of the surface lignin and hemicelluloses also expose more active hydroxyl groups from cellulose to react with matrix, which increase the chemical bonding between fibre and matrix. Furthermore chemical treatments increase the fibre surface roughness, which increase the mechanical bonding and friction between fibre and matrix. All these lead to the increase of mechanical properties. It is also noticed that excessive treatment is detrimental to the fibre internal structure itself and weaken the fibre.

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